

“Babies being killed”: A pragma-dialectical analysis of Biden’s justification for the war on Gaza

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Abstract

The escalation of war in the Gaza strip, following the October 7, 2023 Hamas attack has reignited questions about the justifications of disproportionate violence. In the wake of the attack, Israel launched a large-scale ground invasion that has left thousands of civilian deaths. President Biden responded with unwavering support for Israel. Through a pragma-dialectical analysis of Biden’s early speeches, this study interrogates the argumentation strategies deployed to legitimise Israel’s aggression on over two million civilian residents. Analysis reveals that Biden’s rhetoric derailed from measured condemnation into fear-driven moral polarization that invokes Holocaust and 9/11 memories to transform moral support into an international ‘duty’ to defend the “Jews around the world”. Each statement builds upon its predecessor to progressively marshal ad hominem and ad-baculum arguments that justify an “overwhelming” war. The findings contribute insights into the way language may be deployed in political discourse to mask asymmetries in power and suffering and eventually effect a shift from moral alignment into coercive persuasion in the justification of state violence.

67

Keywords

Argumentation strategies, Biden, fallacious argumentation, October 7th, pragma-dialectics, the Israeli Palestinian conflict

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Introduction

Twenty months after Israel's aerial bombardment and ground invasion of the Gaza strip, at the time of writing, the Palestinian civilian death toll is over 61.000 people, most of whom are women and children, according to the latest figures from the Palestinian Ministry of Health (Al Jazeera, 2025). Israel's on-going aggression on Gaza is "the latest and most sustained attack that follows other major bombing campaigns (in 2008–09, 2012, 2014, 2022), as well as more sporadic but regular rounds of targeted killing and bombardment" (El-Shewy, Griffiths, & Jones, 2024). The current assault continues unabated as the United States extends its intelligence, political and military support to the Israeli offensive. This escalating military operation that is wreaking havoc on the lives of civilians, wiping out infrastructure, and spilling over to "regionally to multiple countries, including Lebanon, Iran, Yemen, Syria, Jordan, and Iraq" claims to aim at ridding Gaza of Hamas and making it a 'safer' place for Gazans (El Damanhoury, Saleh, & Lebovic, 2025). The fallout from the war on Gaza and the death toll, however, not only invalidate this proclaimed objective but point at further radicalization and animosity in the aftermath of this relentless aggression.

In this context, the U.S. President Joe Biden played a key role in promoting and disseminating narratives that portray Israel's invasion of the Gaza strip on Gaza not as an act of aggression, but as a legitimate exercise of self-defence. In several official statements and speeches, President Biden uses emotionally charged language, including references to "babies being killed", to justify the United States' unconditional support for Israel's offensive. This type of rhetoric significantly influences how both American and global audiences perceive the conflict and shifts attention away from humanitarian concerns toward a simplified narrative of good versus evil. While the physical devastation in Gaza is evident, Biden's language contributes to a less evident but equally potent form of warfare: to legitimise the use of indiscriminate force by relying on persuasive, albeit fallacious, argumentation.

Moreover, Biden's rhetoric highlights the way political leaders often resort to familiar fallacies, such as emotional appeals and threats, to secure political support and assert moral authority. Biden's rhetoric is designed to shield U.S. foreign policy and Israeli military incursions from criticism in the face of global condemnation of the continuing civilian casualties and humanitarian violations in Gaza. These rhetorical choices do not just serve to sideline alternative perspectives and suppress potential open debate and counterarguments, but also risk justifying excessive military action under the banner of moral duty and historical parallels. By invoking trauma, such as 9/11, and existential threats, such as the Holocaust, Biden consolidates the U.S.–Israel alliance through appeals to collective trauma and fear.

The present study offers an analysis of Biden's political rhetoric using pragma-dialectics – an analytical framework that highlights the conflict between persuasive tactics and logical debate in public discourse. Van Eemeren and Grootendorst (2004) explain that strategic manoeuvring is a key part of argumentation, where speakers try to balance being persuasive with staying within the bounds of fair discussion. When this balance is lost – because of fallacies or manipulation of the debate framework – the goal of rational dialogue is replaced by confusion or distortion. The study seeks to examine whether Biden's rhetoric crosses

that line by using emotionally charged but logically weak arguments to stifle opposition, justify military aggression, and promote a simplified one-sided story of a deeply complex conflict.

The study explores these rhetorical strategies in detail to examine how fallacious argumentation can distort political discourse and undermine rational policymaking. By analysing a set of key statements delivered by President Biden between October 7 and October 18, 2023, this article identifies recurring fallacies, the contexts in which they appear, and their broader implications for the ongoing loss of civilian lives and continued humanitarian violations. The following research questions guide this inquiry:

1. What fallacious argumentation strategies are used in Biden’s justification of Israel’s war on Gaza?
2. In what ways do these strategies represent derailments of strategic manoeuvring within the pragma-dialectical framework?
3. What insights does pragma-dialectics offer into the role of coercive argumentation in shaping political narratives to advance ideological agendas?

Literature Review

The roots of Israel’s military confrontations with Gaza trace back to the aftermath of the 1948 Arab-Israeli war, when hundreds of thousands of Palestinian refugees fled or were expelled from their homes and many settled in Gaza under Egyptian administration (Pappé, 2007; Morris, 2004). Following Israel’s occupation of the Gaza Strip in 1967 during the Six-Day War, the territory became a focal point of resistance and repression, marked by cycles of uprising, military crackdowns, and escalating tensions (Finkelstein, 2014). The First Intifada (1987-1993) and the Second Intifada (2000-2005) were particularly significant, as they prompted harsh military responses and laid the groundwork for Israel’s evolving security doctrine concerning Gaza (Milton-Edwards & Farrell, 2010). Although Israel carried out a unilateral disengagement in 2005, removing its military forces and settlements from the Strip, it retained control over Gaza’s airspace, maritime borders, and crossings. These conditions led the United Nations and other international legal bodies to continue recognizing Gaza as an occupied territory (Institute for the Study of War, 2025). Over the years, Israel has launched multiple military operations in Gaza, the most devastating of which is the on-going assault beginning on October 7th, 2023. The growing civilian casualties and infrastructural devastation have raised urgent questions about the proportionality, legality and long-term implications of sustained conflict on an already besieged population. Over 61,000 Palestinians have been killed, most of them women and children, and the Strip’s infrastructure has been decimated (AJLabs, 2023). As the war spills into neighbouring countries such as Lebanon, Syria, and Iran (at the time of writing), the conflict is no longer a localized military campaign but a regional crisis with global repercussions (Norwegian Refugee Council, 2025).

For decades, the conflict has attracted sustained scholarly attention across a wide range of academic disciplines, particularly those concerned with the role of language in shaping political narratives and legitimising violence in asymmetrical conflicts. Linguistic analyses of political rhetoric on the war in Gaza have uncovered how language functions as a tool of

ideological framing, delegitimization, and moral justification. Early studies using Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) focused on how mainstream Western media disproportionately frames Palestinian actors as aggressors and Israel as a reactive democracy (Philo & Berry, 2004; Chouliaraki, 2009). More recent studies extend these findings to political rhetoric, demonstrating how different media, such as Aljazeera English and BBC, employ different strategies in patterns of quotations, labelling and blame, thereby constructing their own narratives that blur legal and ethical lines in the service of strategic interests (El Damanhoury et al. 2025). Other studies (e.g., Ahmed, Abed, & Hussain, 2022) show that the terms “terrorism” and “Islamic militants” are strategically employed to sanitize military aggression while criminalizing Palestinian resistance. Metaphor analysis has also proven fruitful in revealing underlying conceptualizations, such as Israel being portrayed as “a ship sailing through stormy seas,” while the Palestinians are framed as “a snake that keeps biting,” (Sharaf Eldin, Hamouda, Reda Ali, & Mohamed, 2024). Moreover, corpus linguistics approaches have shown statistically significant patterns in collocational choices that reinforce stereotypes and asymmetries (Aljoundi, 2024). Recent work by Abualadas (2024) investigates Arabic-English translation discrepancies in media coverage, revealing purposive re-labelling, selective omissions and euphemisms that obscure the scale of Palestinian suffering. Collectively, these studies highlight how linguistic framing not only shapes international narratives, principally U.S. narratives. but also acts as a mechanism of power that shapes public opinion and delineates the boundaries of empathy and blame.

Zooming in on the specific concern of this paper, i.e., the discursive role of U.S. presidential rhetoric in influencing the course of the conflict, existing research demonstrates that such discourse, rooted in a historically skewed alignment with Israeli interests, often relies on delegitimising strategies to construct dominant narratives, marginalize dissenting perspectives and ultimately justify military action. The U.S. presidential rhetoric on Gaza, in particular, has consistently reinforced the U.S.-Israeli strategic partnership through a blend of emotional appeals and historical analogies. Earlier analyses of President George W. Bush’s post-9/11 discourse linked Israeli security with global counterterrorism, framing Palestinian resistance as part of a broader “axis of evil” (Mearsheimer & Walt, 2008). Under President Obama, rhetorical shifts included calls for restraint and the right of Palestine to exist access, but the underlying alignment with Israeli security interests remained intact (Terry, 2017). Donald Trump’s presidency amplified the pro-Israel discourse, notably through the relocation of the U.S. embassy to Jerusalem and support for the Abraham Accords, actions that are widely perceived as dismissive of Palestinian statehood aspirations (Rynhold, 2022). Recent scholarship on President Joe Biden’s rhetoric since the October 2023 war highlights a return to emotionally charged rhetoric and skewed moral binaries that frame the conflict in simplified, one-sided terms. Biden’s frequent invocation of trauma-related narratives, i.e., references to the Holocaust, serves to frame Israel’s actions as ethically necessary (Wroblewski, 2025). At the same time, these rhetorical choices marginalize calls for a ceasefire, downplay Palestinian suffering, and position dissenting voices as morally suspect or politically disloyal. Emerging research by Orhan (2024) argues that the Biden’s administration rhetoric represents a significant case of discursive coercion, in which logical reasoning gives way to appeals to fear and unconditional solidarity. Hamas actions are compared to the worst version of ISIS but Israel’s human rights violations, which are “so flagrant”, are disregarded and instead are projected as necessary action to make the world a safer place (Orhan, 2024, p. 57). These

studies call for greater scrutiny of how presidential discourse functions not merely to inform but to mobilize public sentiment in support of contentious policies.

While many studies have analysed the Israeli Palestinian conflict, there remains a notable gap in systematic pragma-dialectical analyses of recent American rhetoric on Gaza, with a focus on the justifications for the 2023–2024 Gaza war. Specifically, although some studies have used discourse-based approaches such as critical discourse analysis, metaphor analysis, collocation, and framing analysis to problematize fallacious reasoning and persuasive language in American presidential rhetoric on the Palestinian issue, few directly apply the pragma-dialectical framework to scrutinize how strategic manoeuvring by high-level political figures like President Joe Biden may derail reasonableness in public discourse. Furthermore, the consequences of these rhetorical practices on public perception of the conflict and its outcomes, particularly regarding accountability and justification for the war’s human toll, remain underexplored. By addressing this gap, the present study contributes to understanding the way presidential rhetoric can function as a discursive tool to legitimise state violence, marginalize dissent, and shape public perception in times of war.

Methods

Data

The data for this study is constituted by President Joe Biden’s official rhetoric during the early phase of the conflict. Specifically, it consists of four official speeches and statements delivered by President Biden between October 7 and October 18, 2023, in response to the Hamas-led attacks in Israel and the subsequent escalation of military operations in Gaza. These texts were retrieved from the official White House website and are publicly accessible primary sources that represent the administration’s official narrative during the initial and most critical phase of the conflict. The selected documents are as follows:

1. Statement from President Joe Biden Condemning Terrorist Attacks in Israel (October 7, 2023)
2. Remarks by President Biden on the Terrorist Attacks in Israel (**October 7, 2023**)
3. Remarks by President Biden on the Terrorist Attacks in Israel (October 10, 2023)
4. Remarks by President Biden on the October 7th Terrorist Attacks and the Resilience of the State of Israel and Its People (October 18, 2023, Tel Aviv, Israel)

These texts have been selected for their direct relevance to the aims of this study, which investigates the discursive strategies employed in U.S. presidential rhetoric to legitimise military action in the context of the 2023 Gaza war. All four texts were issued during the early stages of the conflict, a period in which rhetorical framing plays a critical role in shaping international narratives, public perception and the future course of action. The texts capture key moments of the U.S. official response, including demonization of Hamas, affirmation of U.S.-Israel solidarity, and influencing global and domestic courses of action. As formal articulations of state power, these texts serve not only as declarations of policy but also as instruments of ideological positioning and influence. Their analysis

is therefore essential to understanding how language is strategically employed to frame asymmetrical violence, silence opposition, and justify political action on the world stage, which are key concerns of the present study.

Procedure

This study employs a pragma-dialectical framework by drawing on the theoretical contributions of van Eemeren and Grootendorst (1992, 2004). The framework integrates two complementary dimensions: a pragmatic component concerned with the communicative function of language and a dialectical component focused on the evaluation of argumentative structures and the identification of fallacious reasoning across different discourse genres.

From a pragmatic perspective, the study attends to how utterances function as performative acts (e.g., as warnings, threats, or moral judgments) by drawing upon research work in speech act theory. The speech acts will be analysed not simply as isolated expressions but as moves within a broader argumentative strategy aimed at persuasion, positioning, or justification. On the dialectical side, the focus lies in uncovering how argumentation is organized, which strategies are employed to advance claims, and where violations of rational-critical argument may occur. The analysis seeks to detect fallacies, assess whether argumentative moves comply with logical reasoning, and consider how manipulative intent may override dialectical integrity.

The analysis proceeds chronologically across Biden's four statements. The goal is to show how each successive message amplifies rhetorical pressure, deploying and escalating fear, moral labelling, threat, and omission to create a cumulative effect that ultimately closes space for rational or critical engagement. The analytical procedure begins with identifying potentially manipulative elements in Biden's discourse, particularly those that present a skewed framing of the conflict. Next, the study evaluates how appeals to fear or urgency may function to pressure audience acceptance without adequate argumentative support. This includes evaluating the contextual appropriateness of any claims that invoke authority, morality, or international security. Strategic discourse manoeuvres are analysed using principles of practical reasoning outlined in Walton (2000), which will allow for an examination of how conclusions are constructed, alternatives excluded, and agency and blame assigned.

In doing this, the study aims to reveal how U.S. presidential discourse, particularly in times of international crisis, can function not only to inform but to persuade, justify, and delegitimize within a framework that may obscure the realities of the conflict it describes.

Results

This section offers a pragma-dialectical analysis of the four addresses and statements made by President Biden in response to the Hamas-led attacks in Israel and the subsequent escalation in Gaza. The analysis draws upon the theoretical foundations of pragma-dialectics (van Eemeren & Grootendorst, 1992, 2004) and Walton's (2000) typology of argumentation strategies and seeks to understand how language is employed to legitimise

Israel’s military aggression. The findings are organized chronologically to trace the intensification of the discourse and its drift from rational to emotionally charged and coercive argumentation.

October 7, 2023 Initial First Statement

The first official response by President Biden came approximately ten hours after the Hamas attack. This quick response demonstrated Biden’s intention to assure solidarity with and moral support for Israel and pre-empt dissent to a military offensive, as will be shown in the analysis below.

The opening statement is the shortest in length (n=162 words). The timing and brevity of the statement are rhetorically significant. This swift intervention functions not just as an expression of grief, but also as a normative positioning. Early in the statement, Biden uses ad hominem labelling to delegitimise Hamas and close any space for rational debate. He describes the attack as “horrific” and “appealing”, labels Hamas fighters as “terrorists”, and asserts that terrorism “is never Justified”. In the next sentence, he declares that “Israel has the right to defend itself and its people”. The assertion of these absolutes in the first four sentences of the statement serves to establish a moral dichotomy that defines right and wrong in stark, uncompromising terms and creates a baseline against which all subsequent actions and political rhetoric will be judged.

Against the background of this dichotomy, Biden issues a covert ad baculum argument containing an implicit threat without overt ultimata. He warns “any other party hostile to Israel” from taking advantage of the situation. The ad baculum, against the background of emotional connection with Israel and the demonized opponent, makes dissent morally suspect and indeed a betrayal of collective grief. To deepen the sense of shared sorrow, Biden brings the tragedy home, invoking the families affected, lives cut short, and the injured. This emotional appeal casts Israel in the role of the victim, especially as the Palestinian civilians or Gazans remain noticeably absent from the statement. This one-sided victim narrative serves to further emphasize the moral duty and responsibility of the U.S. administration. Accordingly, the statement closes by emphasizing that the U.S. is “tracking this situation closely” and will maintain direct communication with Prime Minister Netanyahu, who is referred to by name and official title three times within this tightly packed statement of condemnation. This deliberate repetition reinforces the unwavering alignment with the Israeli leadership.

October 7, 2023 Follow-Up Remarks

The second response by President Biden came five hours later the same day. The follow-up remarks retain the moral dichotomy (friends vs. terrorists) established in the first statement and escalate the rhetoric from a moral stance into a more forceful position aimed at coercing consensus and shielding criticism. Additionally, warnings evolve into threats that are globally and diplomatically enforced, as will be shown in the analysis below.

The follow-up remarks are about three times the length of the first statement (n=471 words). Building on the moral foundation established in the first statement, Biden intensifies his ad

hominem approach by reminding the audience that “the people of Israel are under attack, orchestrated by a terrorist organization, Hamas.” By repeatedly describing Hamas as a “terrorist organization,” (five times in this statement), Biden continues to strip it of any political legitimacy, reducing the entire exchange to an absolute moral conflict. Hamas is not a political actor but a moral villain, beyond redemption or dialogue. The statement moves quickly from moral clarity into coercion. Biden asserts, “We will not ever fail to have their back,” which serves as an implicit *ad baculum*. Any hostile actor will face consequences. He then reiterates: “Israel has the right to defend itself ... Full stop.” This echoes the absolutism from the first statement and closes any room for debate on Israel’s right to military response. The repetition of these phrases within hours escalates the tone from moral support to unyielding moral command.

Biden advances the emotional appeal with vivid imagery, viz., “thousands of rockets,” “innocent people murdered,” “entire families taken hostage,” and “lost a piece of their soul”. The graphic detail evokes horror and creates another dichotomy between humanity (Israeli vulnerable civilians) and terror (Hamas), confirming the eristic tactic of shifting from reasoned debate into emotionally charged moral assertion. This mirrors the first statement’s tactic of directing the listener’s instinctive sympathy for Israel and deepening moral condemnation of the other side – the Palestinians or Gazans, who are again selectively omitted from the narrative. Another ideological omission in the statement is reference to the historical conflict, occupation, or suffering endured by the Palestinians. This selective emphasis constructs a one-sided narrative that ignores the broader historical framework in favour of immediate moral clarity.

In this context, Biden escalates the commitment to supporting Israel from empathy into actionable deterrence: “We will not ever fail to have their back” and the “United States stands with the people of Israel”, which is repeated ten times in the statement, albeit using different wording each time. This is another implicit *ad baculum* – a threat to any party that might oppose or criticize Israel and a clear intensification from the moral support of the first statement. To ensure coercively holding up opposition, Biden details his communications with Jordan, Congress, intelligence, Egypt, Turkey, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Oman, the UAE, European partners and even the Palestinian Authority. This regional and international alliance positions Israel’s cause as universally recognized and further isolates Hamas, especially as Arab leaders and the Palestinian Authority are invoked. This is yet another *cover ad baculum*: any actor outside this coalition risks moral and political exclusion.

The ‘global coalition’ narrative is followed by a personal grief narrative that deepens the moral alignment with Israel and further invalidates potential voices of dissent: “Jill and I are praying for those families ... We grieve with those who have lost their loved ones...”. The statement closes with a historical narrative to supplement the personal, human and political narratives. Biden says the U.S. recognized Israel “11 minutes after its founding, 75 years ago”. Invoking the historical context serves to affirm Israel’s legitimacy and intensify U.S. support from a moral into a foundational alliance. By doing so, any Palestinian historical grievances and narratives are pre-emptively dismissed. Compared to the initial statement, this statement marks a shift from moral support into a coordinated alliance rooted in historical entitlement in order to defend the state of Israeli and cut off rational space for discussion or dissent.

October 10, 2023 Remarks

The third address, delivered three days after the initial attack, significantly escalates the presidential rhetorical. Building on the moral absolutes and implicit deterrence of the first statement, and the emotionally charged warnings and coalition signals of the second, this speech intensifies its persuasive effect through the use of vivid imagery, explicit ad baculum appeals, and demonizing language, Biden reinforces the moral divide between “good” and “evil” and continues to strategically omit historical context. The following analysis explores how these rhetorical manoeuvres amplify coercion and further foreclose critical debate with military response.

The third official response is almost three times the length of the second statement (n=1296). The first line of the address intensifies the ad hominem tactic beyond the familiar “terrorist” labelling. The description of Hamas as “pure, unadulterated evil” that has been “unleashed upon the world” not only deepens the moral divide between “us” vs. “them” but also sets the stage for imperative military action in order to neutralise this “evil”. The demonization of Hamas and victimization of Israel is carried forward through a series of “appalling” images depicting graphic details: “bloody hands of the terrorist organization Hamas”, “1000 civilians slaughtered”, “Parents butchered”, “entire families slain”, “Young people massacred”, “Women raped” and “paraded as trophies”, and “babies being killed”. Invoking “babies”, an emblem of innocence, helps Biden unleash a fear-loaded rhetorical lever that not only demonizes Hamas but also accentuates its ‘genocidal’ intent, viz., “to kill Jews”. This tactic intensifies the ad hominem fallacy argument and morally prohibits questioning of the extent of Israel’s upcoming military response.

The “stomach-turning” images serve not only to generate moral outrage but also to justify the extreme use of force. Biden’s implicit ad baculum argument that dissent will incur consequences now morphs into an explicit warning “to any country, any organization, anyone thinking of taking advantage of this situation”. He adds that “if the United States experienced what Israel is experiencing, our response would be swift, decisive, and overwhelming.” To sustain this one-sided narrative, Biden continues to completely leave out any mention of Palestinian suffering or the historical context of the conflict. He repeats “There is no justification for terrorism” and “There is no excuse,” throughout the statement to ensure that counterarguments are pre-empted and that the discourse remains unidirectional.

The accumulation of vivid imagery throughout the statement highlights the ‘unproved’ “bloodthirstiness” of Hamas and also to strengthen the legitimising argument. Israel’s “right” to retaliation turns into a “duty” not only to defend the people of Israel but to fight off the ‘annihilation of the Jews’. To further strengthen the fear appeal, Biden invokes Holocaust memory – “brought to the surface painful memories ... scars ... antisemitism and genocide of the Jewish people.” The Holocaust reference intensifies the fear-based argument and escalates it from justified defence into a moral imperative against existential threats. It also amplifies the ad hominem argument by equating Hamas not merely with modern extremist groups but with a historical and symbolic enemy of an ethnic and religious people. The generational trauma associated with the holocaust reinforces the victim narrative and the ad baculum logic: if the Holocaust was ignored in its time, the

world now “will not stand by and do nothing again. Not today, not tomorrow, not ever.” Inaction, or even counterargument, becomes complicity not only in the present “evil” but also in historical atrocities. By drawing on Holocaust memory to legitimise the war, the argument transitions from reasoned justification to emotional moral command. It forecloses debate on proportionality of the response, civilian protection, or legal restraints. The argument shifts from rational discourse into an emotionally charged and historically justified imperative.

After establishing the right, indeed duty, to respond, Biden re-affirms the commitment of the United States, and its allies, to support this effort. He identifies “at least 14 American civilians killed” and positions the U.S. itself as under threat, which converts solidarity with Israel from moral to existential for both Israel and the U.S. This shift frames the war as a matter of global security, not merely regional defence. It’s no longer “Israel’s right” but “our security,” which is an extension of the coalition rhetoric from the previous statement. European powers, including the U.K., Germany and France, are now invoked, in addition to the Arab leaders invoked earlier, which strengthens the argument from consensus and delegitimises any opposition and portrays Israel’s defence as the purpose of a global security effort. This is followed by another *ad baculum* appeal, with Biden specifying “additional military assistance” and the deployment of “USS Gerald R. Ford Carrier Strike Group” to the Eastern Mediterranean. Biden concludes by repeating that U.S.–Israel alignment is anchored in historical memory to further enhance the historical legacy of the State of Israel.

In this third address, Biden merges moral outrage, national security concerns, and international military coordination to transform the supportive narrative from the previous two addresses into an imperative war narrative with little room for deliberation. This amounts to a progressive narrative intensification, from condemnation and labelling to normative closure backed by fear-driven rhetoric and threats.

October 18, 2023 Remarks

The fourth presidential address, delivered on October 18, represents the apex of Biden’s rhetorical escalation. At nearly 2292 words, this long speech amplifies the persuasive impact through vivid imagery of beheadings, invoking 9/11 and recalling the “worst ravages of ISIS”. The following analysis examines how each rhetorical tactic functions to intensify coercion and indeed speed up the military response.

The last address examined in this study comes against the backdrop of Israel’s complete siege of Gaza and its deadly bombing of the al-Ahli Arab Hospital the previous day, which killed hundreds of Palestinians, including ‘children, infants, and elderly grandparents’. Biden, speaking from Israel this time, starts the speech by reiterating support for Israel and expressing solidarity with the Israeli families by telling them “You are not alone”. Then he goes to foreground Israeli civilian losses and minimize Palestinian civilian tragedy by continuing the pattern of demonization through loaded descriptors: “Children slaughtered. Babies slaughtered. Entire families massacred. Rape, beheadings, bodies burned alive”. The *ad hominem* labelling, while constructing Hamas as an existential threat, is meant to justify the severe military countermeasures. Accordingly, the hundreds of Palestinian

civilian deaths in the hospital attack are mentioned in passing against a barrage of graphic details describing Israeli victims through graphic imagery of “beheadings” and “bodies burned alive,” and concrete, relatable experiences referencing “the scent when you open the closet door” and “the morning coffee you shared together.”

Biden escalates fear-based rhetoric by constructing Hamas as a global menace. He claims the group’s actions “recall the worst ravages of ISIS, unleashing pure unadulterated evil upon the world”. This not only amplifies his earlier ad hominem labelling but equates Hamas with one of the most universally condemned terrorist entities. He then compares the attack to “fifteen 9/11s”, which constructs the attack as a catastrophe of global proportions. In so doing, Biden redefines Israel’s security as synonymous with global safety and equates defending Israel to protecting “the world”. This rhetorical fusion of graphic emotion and collective insecurity derails rational argument into a shock-induced moral imperative in defence of ‘universal safety’. In this frame, only Israeli lives matter and Palestinian civilian deaths are “mistakes” that are not unexpected during wartime. “There’s always costs,” is Biden’s response to the Gazan civilian casualties.

Biden acknowledges Palestinian suffering regarding the hospital blast and brings up humanitarian assistance to Gaza but these references remain minimal and contextualized as conditional: “If Hamas diverts the assistance... it will end.” This framing is consistent with the narrative of ensuring that Israel’s victims and Israel’s security remain predominant while humanitarian concerns remain subordinate or conditional. Biden also maintains rhetorical absolutes: “There is no rationalizing it. Period.”, “You are not alone.”, “Don’t. Don’t. Don’t.” These phrases act as closure devices, indicating there is no room for rational discourse.

To divert attention from Gaza onto the Israeli narrative, Biden elevates the conflict into a religious and existential narrative of Jewish survival. He declares “You are a Jewish state,” refers to the October 7th as “the deadliest day for the Jewish people since the Holocaust,” and compares the survivors to Prophet Moses. These rhetorical tools elevate Israel’s security from a political necessity to a sacred duty. To ensure that Israel remains “a safe place for the Jewish people of the world”, Biden issues an ad baculum appeal to adversaries of Israel. He escalates U.S. military involvement, funding and naval presence in the area: “We have moved U.S. military assets to the region, including positioning the USS Gerald R. Ford carrier strike group in the Eastern Mediterranean, with the USS Eisenhower on the way, to deter – to defer further aggression against Israel and to prevent this conflict from spreading”.

Having established Israel’s right to defend itself and its security being a global duty, Biden repeatedly reiterates that “the United States stands with Israel” throughout the address. This refrain functions as more than mere solidarity; it is a rhetorical anchor that affirms unwavering partnership and aligns U.S. identity with Israel’s fate. By weaving the phrase into nearly every segment of the speech, Biden closes off moral or political space for dissent. In doing so, he transforms support from a declarative stance into a discursive imperative, suggesting that advocating for Israel’s security is synonymous with defending universal values and the interests of the United States itself.

Conclusion

This study set out to examine how President Biden's rhetoric following the October 2023 Hamas attack used argumentative strategies to justify, indeed accelerate, Israel's large-scale military aggression against Gaza's civilian population. Through the pragma-dialectical approach, analysis has traced how coercive and emotion-laden language functions to shape public narrative, shut down dissent, and equate international security with the survival of Israel. By tracing the escalation in tone and argumentative form across the first four statements, it becomes clear that Biden's rhetoric increasingly relies on manipulative labelling, ad baculum threats, moral absolutism, and fallacies in consequence-based reasoning to pre-emptively foreclose disagreement, normalize disproportionate use of violence war, and convert moral support into moral "duty".

In addressing these concerns, the present study proposed three research questions. The first one sought to trace the fallacious argumentation strategies used in Biden's justification of Israel's war on Gaza. Analysis has revealed that Biden draws from a rhetorical toolkit that previous U.S. presidents had relied on to justify wars. Biden's use of ad hominem labelling (e.g., terrorists, pure unadulterated evil, worst ravages of ISIS, deadliest day for the Jewish people since the Holocaust, fifteen 9/11s, etc.), overt ad baculum threat appeals (notably the positioning of U.S. carrier strike groups as explicit deterrents), and consequence-driven argumentation about global stability is reminiscent of President George W. Bush's rhetoric in the post-9/11 era. Like Biden, Bush used fallacious argumentation to build a 'moral case' for the war on Iraq, based on "adversarial (rather than dialogical) argumentation" (Sahlane, 2012, p. 154). Bush also deployed ad hominem rhetoric (Franck, 2003), fear appeals and threat appeals (Simuziya, 2023) to justify the Iraq War under the guise on 'War on Terror', again by framing opponents as "evil" and "an existential threat" to civilization. Just as Bush's discourse created normative closure and limited public deliberation over military intervention, Biden's speeches similarly pre-empt critique and construct Israeli security as equivalent to global stability.

In relation to the second research question, the analysis demonstrates that Biden's rhetoric breaches key rules in the pragma-dialectical model of argumentation, particularly those governing freedom of critical response, burden of proof, and closure of discussion. In his October 7 initial statement, the rapid moral closure begins with "Terrorism is never justified. Israel has the right to defend itself and its people," which establishes absolute moral terms and leaves no room for contextual inquiry. The follow-up remarks repeat the normative closure and back it up with an implicit ad baculum argument "for any party hostile to Israel" and declarations like "We will not ever fail to have their back." By October 10, Biden escalates the fear appeals by using graphic imagery, including "babies being killed" and elevates the discourse into the realm of Jewish religious identity. He describes the "purpose" of Hamas as the killing of Jews everywhere, constructing the war not merely as geopolitics, but as a holy struggle. He uses explicit ad baculum tactics: "our response would be swift, decisive, and overwhelming" if the U.S. faced similar violence. In the last statement, Biden deepens the emotional leverage by invoking the Holocaust memory and comparing the attack to world-shaping events like 9/11 and Hamas to ISIS. Biden's derailments parallel post-9/11 rhetoric used by President George W. Bush, who framed terrorism as an existential threat, invoked moral

binaries, and demanded allegiance via his “axis of evil” and “you’re either with us or against us” framing (Rojecki, 2008).

As for the third question, pragma-dialectics has proved especially useful in uncovering the way coercive argumentation can be masked as strategic reasoning in political rhetoric. It offers a rigorous framework to assess how emotionally manipulative tactics undermine norms of deliberation and preclude alternative viewpoints. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of how political language functions not merely to inform but to persuade, constrain, and consolidate power. By applying pragma-dialectical theory to the case of Biden’s Gaza speeches, the analysis underscores the broader implications of rhetorical strategies in shaping public narratives and legitimising state violence.

This study is limited by its exclusive focus on the first four official statements delivered by President Biden in the immediate aftermath of October 7. Their timing, ranging from approximately ten hours to eleven days into the conflict, was crucial for understanding how rhetorical escalation unfolded in real time. However, the decision to concentrate on these four speeches meant that the linguistic analysis could not extend to a broader set of addresses, which might have revealed shifts in rhetoric as international pressure grew. Consequently, the data set size is intentionally narrow to allow for in-depth pragma-dialectical analysis. This, however, limits generalizability. To expand on these findings, future research could undertake a comparative analysis of Biden’s rhetoric with later statement and with that of President Trump, particularly during the 2024-25 Gaza crisis. Applying the same pragma-dialectical criteria to a corpus of Trump’s public addresses and interviews could reveal whether similar derailments of strategic manoeuvring, such as normative closure and demonizing opponents, persist. Additionally, multimodal discourse analysis incorporating media framing or audience reception studies would further enrich our understanding.

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